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ТАДҚИҚОТ ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ | JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

ABDUGANIEVA Zebuniso Abduhafizovna
(PhD)

Uzbekistan State World Languages University
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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GENRE ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH ARTICLE ABSTRACTS IN THE FIELD OF APPLIED LINGUISTICS

ANNOTATION

An abstract is a promotional genre that plays a crucial role in determining the fate of research papers. Despite significant attention given to the rhetorical organization of abstracts in academic discourse, there is a lack of studies that have investigated genre analysis of abstracts in the field of applied linguistics. This article focuses on the genre analysis of research article abstract and aims to identify common structural approaches to developing a well-crafted abstract in this field. By using Pho's (2008) five-move model for framework, twelve research article abstracts were randomly chosen from journal Applied Linguistics for analysis. It was found that only 25% of abstracts adhered to a five-move model.

The most prevalent moves were move 3 methodology, followed by purpose and result. It can be concluded that the purpose, methodology, and result of the research are obligatory elements of research article abstracts, while the introduction can be optional. Teaching the generic structure of abstracts from this journal can be beneficial for postgraduate students conducting research, particularly in the field of applied linguistics.

Key words: scientific discourse, genre, move analysis, research article, genre-based approach, ESP.

AMALIY TILSHUNOSLIK SOHASIDA ILMIY MAQOLA ABSTRAKTLARINING JANR TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Abstrakt bu ilmiy tadqiqot maqolalarining taqdirini hal qiluvchi janrlardan biridir. Ilmiy diskursda abstraktlarning retorik tuzilishini o'rganishga katta e'tibor berilayotganligiga qaramasdan, amaliy tilshunoslik sohasida abstraktlarning janr tahlili kam o'rganilgan. Ushbu maqola tadqiqot maqolasi abstraktlarining janr tahliliga qaratilgan va ushbu sohada yaxshi tayyorlangan abstraktlarni yaratishda umumiy tizimli yondashuvlarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Fo (2008) ning besh harakat modelidan foydalangan holda, o'n ikkita tadqiqot maqolasi abstraktlari tahlil qilish uchun "Amaliy tilshunoslik" jurnalidan tasodifiy tanlab olindi. Aniqlanishicha, abstraktlarning atigi 25 foizi besh-harakatli modelga amal qilgan. Eng keng tarqalgan harakatlar 3-harakat: metodologiya, undan keyin maqsad va natija harakatlari ekanligi aniqlandi.

Xulosa qilish mumkinki, tadqiqotning maqsadi, metodologiyasi va natijasi ilmiy tadqiqot maqolasi abstraktlarining majburiy elementlari bo'lib, kirish qismi esa ixtiyoriy bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu "Amaliy tilshunoslik" jurnalida chop etilgan abstraktlarning umumiy tuzilishini o'rgatish, ayniqsa, amaliy tilshunoslik sohasida tadqiqot olib borayotgan magistrlar uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ilmiy diskurs, janr, harakatlar tahlili, ilmiy maqola, janrga asoslangan yondashuv, maxsus maqsadlarda ingliz tili.

ЖАНРОВЫЙ АНАЛИЗ АБСТРАКТОВ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ СТАТЕЙ В ОБЛАСТИ ПРИКЛАДНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Абстракт - это один из жанров, решающих судьбу научно-исследовательских статей. Несмотря на значительное внимание, уделяемое риторической организации абстрактов в академическом дискурсе, исследований, посвященных жанровому анализу рефератов в области прикладной лингвистики, не хватает. Эта статья посвящена жанровому анализу аннотации исследовательской статьи и направлена на выявление общих структурных подходов к разработке хорошо составленного реферата в этой области. Используя в качестве основы пятиходовую модель Фо (2008), для анализа были случайным образом выбраны двенадцать тезисов исследовательских статей из журнала «Прикладная лингвистика». Было обнаружено, что только 25% тезисов придерживались пятиходовой модели. Наиболее распространенными ходами были методология хода 3, за которыми следовали цель и результат.

Можно сделать вывод, что цель, методология и результат исследования являются обязательными элементами аннотации научной статьи, тогда как введение может быть необязательным. Обучение общей структуре абстрактов из этого журнала «Прикладная лингвистика» может быть полезным для аспирантов, проводящих исследования, особенно в области прикладной лингвистики.

Ключевые слова: научный дискурс, жанр, анализ ходов, научная статья, жанровый подход, Английский для специальных целей.

Introduction

Over recent decades, publishing research papers has become significant not only for scholars who are constantly required to publish their research outcome in highly reputable journals, but also for novice researchers at the university level [Alamri, 2023].

In academic prose, an abstract is an initial stage that editors of prestigious and referred journals consider accepting articles for publication [Duan and Wei, 2021].

The effectiveness of a researcher's work may be compromised if a qualified abstract is not included, as it significantly identifies the likelihood of publication [Tseng, 2011].

It provides a brief summary of a complete article or proposed work which serves as an advertisement [Sheldon & Jackson, 1999]. Therefore, it is regarded as an essential and component of the article. In this regard, research article abstracts have gained the attention of increasing number of researchers in the field of Applied Linguistics for revealing their rhetorical organization and linguistic features.

Research reveals that novice writers encounter challenges in constructing well-written abstracts that are appropriate to the requirements set by their academic discourse. These challenges are even bigger for novice L2 writers who are attempting to publish their research results in highly reputable journals. For example, Busch-Lauer found most papers written by German novice investigators had some linguistic and structural imperfections in their abstracts which could prevent readers to comprehend [Busch-Lauer, 1995].

Li and Ren (2011) also concluded that student writers were insecure and “weak” in abstracts by including the limitations of their research (p. 165). Imparting the genre structure of research article abstracts to L2 postgraduate students is deemed essential to adequately prepare them for the realm of publication [Pho, 2008], facilitating improved engagement within their discourse community [Paltridge, 2012]. Therefore, it is crucial to raise L2 student writers’ genre awareness by giving explicit guidelines to design well-structured abstracts for their research papers.

The primary objective of this paper is to conduct a genre analysis of research article abstracts for utilization in the language classroom of L2 postgraduate students. The paper commences by providing a description of the concept of genre and English for specific purposes approaches to genre analysis. Subsequently, twelve research article abstracts from the Applied Linguistics journal are analyzed using Pho's (2008) model as a conceptual framework. The findings are then compared with existing literature, and the implications of these findings for the language classroom are discussed

Theoretical background

One well-known approach for studying linguistic, rhetorical and textual analysis of academic writing is genre analysis. A definition of genre entails the customary use of language within comparable texts to address recurrent situations [Hyland, 2004].

Martin and Rose (2008) characterize genres as "staged, goal-oriented, and social processes" (p. 6). In a more detailed sense, genres exhibit interactivity as they involve a collective effort for their production, purposefulness as they unfold towards the objectives of their participants, and sequencibility as they typically involve multiple steps to achieve the participants' purposes [Rose, 2012].

Genre studies are generally classified into three main schools by scholars, namely "English for Specific Purposes" (ESP), primarily grounded in Swales's (1990) theory; the "Sydney School of Genre Studies," mainly influenced by the systemic functional linguistics theory of Halliday (1994); and "Rhetorical Genre Studies," which is rooted in first language writing and poststructuralism in North America [Ahn, 2012; Hyon, 2017; Paltridge, 2012]. Although the divergence between the first two schools is diminishing, they are not yet formally categorized as one school [Hyon, 2017]. Each school adopts a distinct approach to conducting genre analysis, with a focus on ESP approaches in this paper due to the prevalence of this pathway in previous research on research article abstracts.

ESP approaches to genre analysis

Swales (1990) defines genre as a group of “communicative events”, in which the participants have similar “communicative purposes” [Swales, 1990 p.58].

That communicative purpose has an impact on a reader to make a decision about a particular genre of a text [Swales, 1990]. However, later he admits that the definition of genre cannot be so clear-cut and prefers to characterize genre in metaphorical ways [Swales, 2004].

He proposes exploring genres with six metaphors each defines various characteristics of genre [Swales, 2004].

These metaphors are “genre as frame” which helps people to communicate easily; “genre as standard” which restricts what is appropriate; and “genre as biological species” which may change over time; “genre as families” in which members may have some differences but still have the same genetic background and “genre as institutions” which has similar concerns, traditions but its members have different roles “genre as speech acts” which constructs a text demanded by a particular situation [Swales, 2004 pp. 61-68].

The participants of same genre may have multiple goals and they may not be similar. Also, the communicative purpose of genre may alter over time [Paltridge, 2012].

The notion of moves is utilized for describing written discourse in ESP school [Paltridge, 2012]. Swales (2004) defines moves as “discoursal or rhetorical units” which demonstrate “coherent communicative functions in a written or spoken discourse” (p. 229). Each move refers to a chunk of text that presents particular a communicative function [Kanoksilapatham, 2007].

Even though, moves may juxtapose with sentences in most cases, they may sometimes be one word or several paragraphs [Hyon, 2017]. This may happen because they play functional roles rather than formal roles in the texts [Can et al, 2016]. Sometimes, these moves may include a number of “steps or sub-moves”, which create a place for moves to “perform their function” [Hyland, 2000]. Concisely, a text consists of moves which serve for communicative purpose of a writer.

Research article abstracts

Abstract is an accurate summary and “purified” representation of full research article, readers decide to continue reading the whole article by looking through the abstract [Swales, 1990]. It is defined as a portrayal or an outline of the much longer text, which gives a reader brief and clear information of the full article [Bhatia, 1993]. Research article abstract is one genre in academic discourse [Hyland, 2000; Martin, 2003] which is regarded as a brief representation of the main features of the research article [Cross & Oppenheim, 2005].

It saves time of a reader, decreases the language barrier, prepares the reader what to read, and provides basic comprehension of the research article [Cross, Oppenheim, 2005]. Therefore, editors of journals usually make a decision whether or not to read a research article by its abstract [El-Dakhs, 2017].

Research on research article abstracts within different disciplines has proliferated in since 2000s when Swales (2004) declared them as “neglected area of research” (p.181). Subsequently, numerous studies have delved into research on abstracts across diverse fields such as medicine, energy, education, and applied linguistics, inspired by this claim [e.g., Can et al., 2016; El-Dakhs, 2018; Gillaerts & Van de Velde, 2010; Huang, 2018; Martin, 2003; Pho, 2008; Samraj, 2005; Tseng, 2011]. In the domain of applied linguistics, research on research article abstracts has predominantly employed the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) approach to genre analysis, as observed in studies by Can et al. (2016), Pho (2008), and Tseng (2011). Utilizing Pho's (2008) model as a framework, the upcoming section of this paper will undertake an analysis of research article abstracts.

Methods

Twelve research article abstracts are randomly chosen from journal *Applied Linguistics* for analysis. This journal was chosen for analysis since it specifically focuses on applied linguistics, making it a suitable choice for our genre analysis. In other words, it provides a concentrated source of research article abstracts in this field. Also, articles published in previous years may provide more stable and available datasets and results for your analysis compared to newer, potentially provisional findings in recent publications.

Therefore, we selected the research article abstracts that are published. Then the abstracts are adjusted for manual genre analysis, removing the research article, the title of it, information about writers, and keywords. Pho's (2008) a five-move model is adopted for analysis. This model is used for framework in our analysis because it has been considered to be more suitable framework for genre analysis of abstracts by the research [Tseng, 2011; Can et al, 2016].

According to Pho (2008) there are five moves in abstracts that indicate macrostructure of whole research article. These moves are “introduction, purpose, method, product, and conclusion” [Pho, 2008].

Similar to Hyland's (2000) model, it also differentiates author's purpose from introduction which was omitted in other models [e.g. Swales, 1990; Bhatia, 1993]. Moreover, it includes questions which Hyland's (2000) model did not contain. This model is used for analysis since these questions make it easy to realize each move in the structure of abstracts. Table 1 illustrates exact functions of each move, questions for finding them and label of each move in this paper.

Moves	Functions	Questions being asked	Label of each move in this paper
Introduction	Situates context of the paper and stimulates the research	What is known in the field?	Move 1
Purpose	Identifies purpose, question hypothesis of the research	What is the study about?	Move 2
Method	Gives knowledge on design, procedures, assumptions, approach	How the research was conducted?	Move3
Result	presents major findings or results, the argument or what was achieved	What was found?	Move 4
Conclusion	Interprets or extends results beyond scope of paper, draws inferences points to applications or broader implications	What do the findings mean? So what?	Move 5

Table 1. A classification of moves (Adopted by Pho, 2008, p. 4)

Results and discussion

As is presented in the table 1 there are exact functions of each move. They may be easily found by asking the questions in the third column of the table. Based on this framework, research article abstracts are analyzed in the present paper. Appendix A provides original texts of all selected abstracts (pp. 16-22). Appendix B demonstrates manual analysis of these abstracts (pp. 23-32). Appendix C provides the resources of the abstracts. The tables below illustrate our findings. The table 2 demonstrates the number and percentage of the abstracts that included exact move, whereas table 3 shows occurrences of moves in each abstract

Moves	Number of abstracts containing move N=12	Percentage of abstracts containing move P=100%
Move 1	6	50%
Move 2	11	92%
Move 3	11	92%
Move 4	12	100%
Move 5	10	83%

Table 2. Frequency of moves in the abstracts

	Move 1	Move 2	Move 3	Move 4	Move 5
Abstract 1	-	+	+	+	+
Abstract 2	-	+	+	+	+
Abstract 3	-	+	+	+	-
Abstract 4	-	+	+	+	+
Abstract 5	-	+	+	+	+

Abstract 6	-	+	+	+	+
Abstract 7	+	-	+	+	+
Abstract 8	+	+	+	+	+
Abstract 9	+	+	-	+	+
Abstract 10	+	+	+	+	-
Abstract 11	+	+	+	+	+
Abstract 12	+	+	+	+	+

Table 3. Appearances of moves in each abstract.

As presented in Table 3, the selected research article abstracts seldom encompassed all five rhetorical moves. Merely 3 out of 12 abstracts contained all the rhetorical moves. A detailed analysis of each move will be expounded upon below.

Move 1: Introduction

This introductory move manifested in 50% of the selected abstracts. Can et al. (2016) posited that this move may encompass several sub-moves, such as articulating current or prior knowledge and delineating a problem. Within our analyzed abstracts, these sub-moves included information about existing knowledge followed by a problem that remained unresolved. For instance, in abstract 11, this move comprised two sub-steps: the first sub-move pertained to current knowledge in the field, while the second sub-move entailed stating a problem to position the author's investigation within the topic (refer to Appendix B on p.31).

Move 2: Purpose

As the second most prevalent move, eleven out of 12 abstracts featured this move. Hence, this move can be deemed a requisite element in the analyzed abstracts. This move may entail sub-moves that elucidate the primary aims or features, research questions, or hypotheses of the research article [Pho, 2008]. All these components were discernible in the selected abstracts. In four out of 12 abstracts, move 2 encompassed two sub-moves, while in most cases, it comprised a single step. For instance, in abstract 1, move 2 comprised two sub-moves: the first sub-move elucidated the main purpose of the research, while the second sub-move articulated the research question of the study (refer to Appendix B on p.23).

Move 3: Method

Similarly, move 3 was present in eleven out of 12 abstracts in the current study. Consequently, this move can also be regarded as one of the most pivotal moves in the abstracts. Only one abstract did not include this move. Move 3 may delineate the design, procedure, data, and occasionally anticipations of the studies [Pho, 2008]. At times, this move may incorporate move 2. For example, in Abstract 8 (refer to Appendix B pp. 28-29), move 2 appears within move 3.

Move 4: Product

The occurrence of move 4 was observed in all abstracts, signifying its paramount importance in research article abstracts. This move pertains to the main results or findings of the research (Hyland). It was succeeded by move 5 in 83% of the abstracts. Merely two authors opted to conclude their abstracts with move 4 (10 out of 12). In comparison to other moves, this move was represented by considerably longer segments of text.

Move 5: Conclusion

Lastly, move 5 was discerned in ten out of 12 analyzed abstracts. According to Hyland (2000), this move may encompass interpretations, implications of research, or discussions of findings vis-à-vis prior research. Within the analyzed abstracts, suggestions and interpretations of results were more prevalent than other components. For instance, in Abstract 3, the researcher provided suggestions for improvement based on his research findings (refer to Appendix B).

In summation, our findings reveal that merely 25% of the abstracts encompassed all five moves. In actuality, only a few abstracts adhered to a five-move model (3 out of 12). The most prevalent moves were move 3 (100%), move 4 (92%), and move 3 (92%). Consequently, they can be considered indispensable elements of research article abstracts. Moreover, move 5 (83%) can also be deemed obligatory stages in the structure of abstracts. However, move 1 emerged as the least frequent element in the analyzed research article abstracts, appearing in merely half of the 12 abstracts. Our findings will be expounded upon in relation to prior research in the subsequent section of this paper.

Our findings are generally consistent with previous research regarding the occurrence of the five-move model and moves 1, 3, and 4 [Can et al., 2016; Pho, 2008; Tseng, 2011]. However, there are some inconsistencies, particularly concerning the frequencies of move 5 [e.g., Hyland, 2000; Santos, 1996]. These discrepancies may be attributed to our focused analysis on a single journal (Applied Linguistics) or shifts in the perceived importance of these moves. Notably, our results align closely with the findings of Can et al. (2016) and Pho (2008). We intend to compare our findings with existing research in the field of applied linguistics, given that our selected journal belongs to this domain.

Santos (1996) was among the pioneering scholars who delved into abstracts in applied linguistics. He examined 94 abstracts and observed that nearly all abstracts included move 2 (93 out of 94) and move 3 (91 out of 94), with approximately 80% featuring move 4 and 50% incorporating move 5. However, only 43% contained move 1 (40 out of 94). Similar to our results, Santos found move 1 to be the least frequent and move 3 to be the most common. Yet, our study revealed a higher frequency of move 5 (83%).

Hyland (2000) conducted a study on abstracts across eight disciplines and noted that only 5% of abstracts encompassed all five moves, which is lower than our findings (16%). Similarly, he observed that half of the abstracts omitted move 1. However, significant differences emerged between his results and ours in terms of move 4 and move 5. While fifty percent of the abstracts lacked move 3 in his study, this proportion was doubled in our research (100%). Furthermore, the occurrence of move 5 was three times lower in his study compared to ours (22% versus 83%).

In a similar study, Pho (2008) compared 30 research article abstracts in applied linguistics (20) and educational technology (10). He found that all abstracts in applied linguistics included move 2 and move 3, while only 45% contained move 1. In contrast to Santos (1996), move 5 was more prevalent (80%) in Pho's study. This finding closely mirrors our results (83%). Pho highlighted that move 5 was more commonly found in applied linguistics journals than in educational technology journals.

Critiquing Pho's (2008) study for its limited number of abstracts analyzed, Tseng (2011) compared research article abstracts from three journals in applied linguistics: TESOL Quarterly, Applied Linguistics, and Language Learning. He emphasized that moves 2, 3, and 4 were crucial elements in abstracts, while move 1 was deemed optional.

Tseng also found a higher percentage of move 5 (74%), although it occurred less frequently than in our study (83%). Additionally, Tseng's study indicated that a four-move model was more prevalent than a five-move model in abstracts, aligning with our findings except for the occurrence of move 4.

Can et al. (2016) analyzed fifty research article abstracts in applied linguistics from the journal ESP. Their findings closely parallel ours, with move 3 being the most frequent (100%), followed by move 2 (96%) and move 4 (90%). Can et al. considered these three moves as the most essential elements in an abstract. They also noted that move 1 was the least frequent element among all moves (54%). Interestingly, they reported a slightly higher occurrence of move 5 (84%) compared to our study's percentage (83%). However, their study found that only 34% of abstracts included all five moves, a lower percentage than in our study (25%).

Conclusion

Scholarly journals rarely accept articles without an abstract [Martin, 2003; Tseng, 2011]. However, regardless of the quality of a researcher's investigation, without an effective abstract for their paper, it may face rejection [Tseng, 2011].

Burgione et al. (2011) asserted that postgraduate students often lack the necessary skills for publication, making this task challenging for them. Teaching genre analysis of research article abstracts can be crucial in preparing L2 postgraduate students for publishing their own papers [Pho, 2008], enabling them to comprehend how authors use language to structure their text and meet readers' expectations [Paltridge, 2012].

The journal *Applied Linguistics* reportedly accepts only 15-20% of articles [Renandya, 2014], indicating their reliability and significance. This statistic suggests that the abstracts of these articles are well-structured since readers often form their initial impressions of a paper based on its abstract [El-Dahks, 2018].

Teaching the generic structure of abstracts from this journal can be beneficial for postgraduate students conducting research, particularly in the field of applied linguistics. This paper provided background information on genre and the approaches to genre analysis in ESP schools. Twelve abstracts were then analyzed using Pho's (2008) model as a framework. It was found that only 25% of abstracts included all five moves. It can be concluded that the purpose, methodology, and findings of research are obligatory elements of research article abstracts, while the introduction can be optional

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Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz